

The Development Of Poverty Reduction In India In The 21st Century In Comparison To The Brics Countries. What Are The Driving Factors And Policy Implications?

Nirali Bhagat

Neerja Modi School, Jaipur, Rajasthan, India

ABSTRACT

This essay analyses the data for poverty between 2010 and 2019. Its purpose is to answer the question, “The development of poverty in India in the 21st century in comparison to the BRICS countries. What are the driving factors and policy implications?” The findings of the study indicate that India has faced a significant poverty crisis and still faces it to an extent in comparison with the other BRICS countries. Hence, this analysis explores the reasons behind as to why India, despite being an economically growing country, still faces issues of poverty and isn't able to eradicate it as efficiently as the mentioned countries. This study is significant in terms of how its findings are crucial for guiding policymakers in crafting effective strategies for sustainable poverty reduction and equitable development. Initially, it talks about the research conducted by other professionals in this field and then goes on to compare the statistics of the BRICS countries. The comparison was based on four indicators: Human Development Index (HDI), Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Consumer Price Index (CPI), and Labour Productivity. The paper explains the graphs developed from the data and reasons as to why such relationships were established. To sum it all up, a few suggestions were proposed towards the end as to how India can improve its poverty levels, answering the research question. For example, one of them was to implement inclusive economic policies with proper government regulation so that the issue of corruption doesn't arise. While, another one was to promote education and skill development so that the labour force expands their skills and competencies, increasing their chances for employment.

Keywords: poverty, Human Development Index, Gross Domestic Product

1. INTRODUCTION

Poverty is an issue that has been prevalent for years. It refers to a condition where a person lacks financial resources to afford basic necessities, for example, food, shelter, water, clothes, etc. Countries have been and are still working in order to eradicate as much poverty as

possible, especially the BRICS countries: Brazil, Russia (Russian Federation), India, China, and South Africa. All five nations have gone through several market reforms, policy implications, and infrastructural developments, which this essay will explore. Furthermore, a statistical analysis is shown through a trend analysis, developing a relationship between the four indicators used to measure poverty: the Human Development Index, Gross Domestic Product, Consumer Price Index, and Labour Productivity. Discussing the results, a few suggestions are laid out as to how India can improve its poverty levels, which in turn would provide it with economic growth.

India felt compelled to adopt policies because other nations were prospering as a result of the favourable effects of their implied policies. A systematic move toward a more open economy that relies more on market forces, a bigger role for the private sector, including foreign investment, and a reform of the role of government were all signals provided by the government. With an average growth rate of almost 6.0 percent throughout the ten-year period from 1992-1993 to 2001-2002, India was one of the emerging nations with the fastest growth rates in the 1990s. Due to an increase in external debt that culminated in the crisis of 1991, growth was unsustainable. Reforms to promote private infrastructure investment have been successful in some locale but not in others. Reforms to the financial sector have advanced in a number of areas, but there are still important questions to be resolved about government control of the banks. The fiscal outcome, on the other hand, indicates a worse situation at the conclusion of ten years than at the beginning. State and federal governments are both experiencing tremendous financial strain, which has a negative impact on their ability to invest in social development and some forms of infrastructure, where the public sector is the only reliable source of funding. In the future, it might be challenging to even maintain 6 percent annual growth, much less jump to 8 percent, if these tendencies are not reversed (Ahluwalia, 2002).

Fan et al. (2005) investigate the dynamics of poverty in rural and urban areas of the economy that are connected with each other socially, economically, and financially. The shift of resources from the rural to the contemporary urban sectors was a crucial component of the industrialization development policies undertaken by developing nations like China and India.

China began its agricultural reform in the late 1970s, whereas India started its macroeconomic reforms in the early 1990s. The study's premise is that, as a result of improved rural-urban linkages, removing urban bias would result in greater agricultural growth and, thus, greater poverty reduction in both rural and urban areas. In contrast to urban

expansion, which helped to lessen poverty in cities, agricultural growth had a stronger influence on rural poverty in China. However, the latter had a detrimental impact on rural areas. China and India had adopted urban-focused development policies. (Fan et al., 2005)

Cornia (2006) argues that today, the primary objective of international development is to reduce poverty. How much pro-poor growth (PPG) will be achieved will have a significant impact on the target of reducing the prevalence of income poverty by half by 2015. How much these three sets of policies speed up growth and enhance income distribution is one of PPG's main concerns. The book briefly discusses the issues with unsustainable policies, macroeconomic populism, and liberal policies before outlining the components of a middle ground strategy that, when tailored to local conditions, can achieve the goal of sustainable growth and poverty reduction. The daily turnover in the foreign exchange market surged from an average of \$0.7 trillion per day in 1992 to \$1.2 trillion per day in 2001. This is more than 50 times the daily trade in goods and services and ten times the daily trade in securities (Cornia, 2006). The economy's susceptibility was further exacerbated by the structural reforms, which over the past 20 years have been a major driver of growth. The dollarization of the economy, the open capital account, and the open trade regime all played a significant role in raising the economy's external vulnerability. A favourable external environment, however, accelerated expansion. The execution of agricultural reform, national discussion, the PRSP process, and other pro-poor policy initiatives have all been hindered by severe governance issues, despite their best intentions. It is helpful to highlight a few macropolitical concerns that should be taken into account as part of a pro-poor policy agenda.

On the other hand, Ghosh (2010) puts forth that growing inequality prevents the poor from benefiting from growth, which is linked to poverty. The many results of economic growth must be determined with the help of government mediation. The structural changes brought about by growth processes aid in creating employment possibilities and a means of subsistence. To lessen hardship and poverty, China's early economic reforms were created. Infrastructure development was given a lot of attention, and some "controlled" trade led to more employment prospects and an industrialisation focused on exports, which became the next driver of growth.

This is in line with the study by Zhang et al.(2020) who also discovered that China has a more export- oriented development strategy as compared with India; therefore, it experiences industrialization at a faster rate. The inequality prevalent in both countries aggravates rather than reduces poverty. Moreover, the adverse contribution of inequality in India is smaller since the income distribution did not deteriorate as much as in China. Secondly, the poverty

reductions in both countries were largely driven by growth. The regression models confirm that China's faster industrialization, urbanisation, and globalisation helped create a vast number of jobs for surplus, low-skilled rural labourers in China, helping lift a huge number of rural residents out of poverty.

China had convenient conditions for poverty reduction through market-led economic growth. Whereas, Brazil and India had changed the course of opportunities to the better-off section of the society; hence, they witnessed no pruning in poverty. However, Ravillion (2011) argues that Brazil had achieved a greater proportion of poverty reduction than India, as it had made use of market-oriented reforms with escalating social policies but still had less economic growth. The reason why China has a high speed in reducing poverty reflects the growth of promoting policy reforms, which have allowed the poor to share more fully in the earnings from growth. The experiences of all three countries verify the importance of keeping inflation under control; periods of higher inflation brought slower progress against poverty in all three countries.

Over the past 30 years, the BRICS (Brazil, Russia, India, China and South Africa) have seen considerable structural change and poverty reduction. The expansion of China's manufacturing industry immediately helped to reduce poverty by providing jobs for rural residents who were otherwise unemployed. Between 1969 and 2006, India saw a significant decline in poverty, thanks to redistributive policies, industrialization, and economic growth. Between 1990 and 2009, Brazil had a 23% decline in poverty, thanks in large part to social security laws and cash transfer programs. Between 2000 and 2011, Russia's poverty rate decreased by more than half, from 29% of the population in 1990 to 12.8% in 2011. The majority of the decrease in poverty in South Africa occurred after 2000, with the rate falling from 24.3% in 1993 to 13.8% in 2008 (Naudé et al., 2015). These experiences offer valuable lessons for low- and middle-income countries seeking structural change and dynamic sectors. Chotia and Rao (2017) emphasise that between 1989 and 2012, the GDP of the BRICS group of countries significantly increased, especially amid the financial crisis. In the BRICS region, this study investigates the effects of infrastructure development on poverty alleviation and rural-urban inequality. In five BRICS countries from 1991 to 2014, the study looks at the connections between infrastructural improvement, economic expansion, and poverty eradication. Results indicate a causal relationship between infrastructure development and economic growth and poverty reduction, which helps reduce poverty and increase growth prospects. This study stresses on the significance of infrastructure growth for attaining economic growth and eradicating poverty.

This is supported by a previous study done by Fosu (2015), who used World Bank data to analyse the transformation of income and inequality changes into poverty reduction in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). It examines the progress made in SSA since the mid-1990s, focusing on the period of growth resurgence. The study finds considerable progress in poverty reduction, contrasting the 1980-1990s period. Income growth has been the main engine for poverty reduction, but inequality has been crucial in some African countries. However, low income levels hinder the effectiveness of income and inequality improvements in poverty reduction. To effectively reduce poverty, the emphasis on growth relative to income distribution should differ across countries (Fosu, 2015).

Whereas the study by Edochie et al. (2022) is focused on India, one of the nations with the greatest populations living below the \$1.90 per person per day international poverty level. The estimates for the poverty rates in urban and rural areas are 7.2 and 12.0 percent, respectively. Moreover, no evidence of an increase in poverty between 2011–12 and 2017–18 is found in the essay.

To further elaborate on the topic of poverty, the following study sought to investigate how poverty and foreign direct investment (FDI) in diverse nations interact. Both developed and growing nations are taken into consideration. Statistics show that a 4-5% FDI share of the GDP aids in limiting the damaging effects of financial crises. By raising people's assets, investment in construction helps preserve or lower the degree of poverty and benefits national economies over the long term. China simultaneously applies a number of theories and models to economic development and the fight against poverty. The study compared the Russian Federation to a number of industrialised and developing nations and experimentally examined the direct effects of GDP, FDI, and construction investment on poverty. Sukhadolets et al. (2021) claim that there is a direct correlation between GDP growth and poverty reduction. In order to decrease poverty, GDP growth must be higher—at least 5-7%—rather than 1-2% annually. Even worldwide financial crises like COVID-19 cannot significantly influence poverty rates, even with negative GDP dynamics, if this GDP growth is sustained for five years. China efficiently applies scientific knowledge by putting the theories of endogenous economic growth into practice.

In contrast to that, Karine (2021) does not limit the research only to China but explores how e-commerce impacts all the BRICS nations—Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa—viewing e-commerce as a way to boost economic development, raise standards of living, and combat poverty. Despite the quick expansion of e-commerce, there are still problems with disproportionate e-commerce in different regions and a lack of coordination.

The essay suggests intensifying collaboration in the areas of infrastructure, instruction, consumer protection, online dispute resolution, and coordinated index policy. China is the only nation that has conducted extensive research on the growth of e-commerce and the alleviation of rural poverty. By addressing shared issues with e-commerce development and ICT applications in rural and distant areas, cross-border e-commerce collaboration might increase e-commerce and retail markets, ensuring prosperity for everybody in the BRICS region.

Zuo (2022) stresses that evidence from recent studies on poverty in general puts forth a question that has called into question the theoretical link between decentralisation and the advantage of representationcum-efficiency in eradicating poverty. Analysing the poverty rate of Mexico, India, and China, he or she finds that the various levels of poverty suggest several types of fundamental issues that must be quickly addressed in order to reduce poverty, as well as various degrees of hurdles and difficulties governments must overcome in order to succeed. Therefore, the institutional designs are being used for the various examples' poverty alleviation initiatives, such as those governing beneficiary choice, resource distribution, and monitoring, as well as the political forces that influence such designs.

To summarise, India and China adopted urban-focused development policies in the 1990s to reduce poverty, but external debt and financial strain on governments hindered growth. Pro-poor growth (PPG) is crucial for reducing income poverty by half by 2015. China's early economic reforms focused on infrastructure development, controlled trade, and industrialization, creating jobs for low-skilled rural labourers. Brazil and India achieved greater poverty reductions than India due to market-oriented reforms and escalating social policies. The BRICS countries have seen structural change and poverty reduction over the past 30 years, with China's manufacturing industry expansion helping reduce poverty. A study found a causal relationship between infrastructure development and economic growth, reducing poverty and increasing growth prospects. E-commerce has also been explored as a way to boost economic development and combat poverty, but issues remain with disproportionate e-commerce and a lack of coordination.

2. DISCUSSION

The data used for the measurement of poverty was the Human Development Index (HDI). It helped to develop an understanding of the standards of living, education (years of schooling), and healthcare of the people in these 5 countries and how they differ from each other. The essay was able to answer the question of how the other countries have grown over the years

and improved their HDI rate, which the other countries were not able to do, especially focusing on India. The second indicator was GDP, i.e., the gross domestic product, of all the BRICS countries, which aided the essay in acquainting the knowledge as to how these countries have evolved over the years from a developing country to a developed country with one of the motives being to eradicate poverty. This also opened the floor to analyze why China was more capable of reducing its poverty rate significantly as compared to countries like South Africa and India, consequently reflecting on what they can do to improve their methods to diminish the level of poverty. Lastly, the essay comments on labour productivity, which looks back upon how the efficiency of workers affects their employment rate, which provides them with their income. Comparing the productivity of the BRICS countries reveals how poverty levels have altered with time. However, the data for labour productivity was available for the year 2017, so the GDP was converted, which was in current US\$, to 2017 by deflating the GDP to that of 2017. The statistics for 2017 were obtained, and the nominal GDP was divided with the real GDP, multiplying the resultant by 100 to get the deflated GDP. All of these indices were available on the World Bank except for labour productivity, which was obtained from the Penn World Table; therefore, it became easier to obtain these statistics for the BRICS countries.

Table 1: Shows the descriptive statistics of HDI, CPI, Labour Productivity, Real GDP of India

Variable	Obs.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min	Max
HDI	10	0.619	0.026	0.575	0.645
CPI	10	6.792	3.084	3.328	11.989
Labour Productivity	10	7.193	1.003	5.699	8.681
Real GDP	10	1975.913	380.21	1430.595	2607.374

Table 2: Shows the descriptive statistics of HDI, CPI, Labour Productivity, Real GDP of
Russia

Variable	Obs.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min	Max
HDI	10	0.822	0.015	0.796	0.845
CPI	10	6.855	3.552	2.878	15.534
Labour Productivity	10	27.953	1.856	24.945	29.996
Real GDP	10	1659.234	334.937	1215	2173.711

Table 3: Shows the descriptive statistics of HDI, CPI, Labour Productivity, Real GDP of
South Africa

Variable	Obs.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min	Max
HDI	10	0.709	0.019	0.675	0.736
CPI	10	5.166	0.862	4.09	6.571
Labour Productivity	10	18.458	0.468	17.884	19.017
Real GDP	10	335.975	28.459	287.219	371.434

Table 4: Shows the descriptive statistics of HDI, CPI, Labour Productivity, Real GDP of
Brazil

Variable	Obs.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min	Max
HDI	10	0.748	0.015	0.723	0.766
CPI	10	5.823	1.981	3.446	9.03
Labour Productivity	10	19.805	0.784	18.865	20.919
Real GDP	10	1188.957	194.172	905.639	1511.438

Table 5: Shows the descriptive statistics of HDI, CPI, Labour Productivity, Real GDP of China

Variable	Obs.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min	Max
HDI	10	0.728	0.024	0.691	0.762
CPI	10	2.59	1.184	1.437	5.554
Labour Productivity	10	10.137	1.192	8.16	11.692
Real GDP	10	12617.83	2778.907	9053.961	17029.39

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Figure 1. - Trend Lines HDI, CPI, Labour Productivity, GDP - Brazil

Ravillion (2011) puts forth that Brazil had achieved a greater proportion of poverty reduction as it had made use of market-oriented reforms with escalating social policies but still there was less economic growth. This is shown in Figure 1. where HDI improves over the years, though at a slow rate, from 0.723 to 0.766, showing an improvement in the standard of living. However, in the year 2011 Brazil had faced a drop in its real GDP portraying less economic growth.

Figure 2. - Trend Lines HDI, CPI, Labour Productivity, GDP - Russia

When observing Figure 2. for HDI and GDP it can be seen that for the whole time period there is no clear trend to be recognized. A sharp drop in 2010 for real GDP was witnessed because non-physical low skilled workers were significantly more likely to become poor than Russians as a whole due to their wages. This discourages them to work efficiently and the output produced is of low quality. The correlation coefficient for HDI and GDP for the entire time period is close to 0 (see Table 7 in the Appendix).

Figure 3. - Trend Lines HDI, CPI, Labour Productivity, GDP - India

In Figure 3. the trend line of labour productivity and HDI of India is close to each other, reflecting that India was one of the emerging nations with the fastest growth rates. Reforms to promote private infrastructure investment had been successful in some locales but not in others. The fiscal outcome, on the other hand, indicates a worse situation at the conclusion of ten years than at the beginning. State and federal governments were both experiencing tremendous financial strain, which had a negative impact on their ability to invest in social development and some forms of infrastructure, where the public sector is the only reliable source of funding (Ahluwalia, 2002). This is why CPI continued to decrease from the year 2013 and even the GDP faced a drop in the year 2017.

Figure 4. - Trend Lines HDI, CPI, Labour Productivity, GDP - China

The trend lines for China can be seen in Figure 4. where the trend line of HDI is very close to that of Labour Productivity. Labour productivity increased from 8.16 to 11.692 because “controlled” trade led to more employment opportunities and an industrialisation focused on exports (Ghosh, 2010). Therefore, more people were at their jobs, earning income, increasing their standard of living; since, they were able to afford the basic necessities like healthcare, food, shelter, education etc. As a result, their HDI rate increased from 0.691 to 0.762. Moreover, China is the only nation that has conducted extensive research on the growth of e-commerce and the alleviation of rural poverty, wanting to make e-commerce one of the significant factors to boost economic growth (Karine, 2021).

Figure 5. - Trend Lines HDI, CPI, Labour Productivity, GDP - South Africa

The graphs for South Africa, in Figure 5., do not show any trend or relationship between HDI, CPI, Labour productivity and real GDP. Though it can be seen that the years 2014 and 2015 were beneficial for South Africa as CPI, Labour productivity and GDP were at its peak. The study by Chotia and Rao portray that from 1991 to 2014 there was a development in infrastructure which helped promote economic growth and reduce poverty levels (Chotia and Rao, 2017), which might be a reason as to why these indicators were at the highest values, during the year 2014 specifically. The HDI rate increased from 0.675 to 0.736 showing that people became better off over the years.

The trend analysis for all the 5 countries shows that there was a growth witnessed in the human development index for all of them, especially China, where it was linear throughout the years. Moreover, for India and China there was a relationship observed for HDI and labour productivity which shows that they were directly proportional to each other. If one increases the other would have the same effect. While the labour productivity for Brazil, Russia and South Africa all faced a sharp decrease in approximately the same years due to

their own reasons, signifying that each of their poverty levels too may have increased during that time.

3. CONCLUSION

This essay sums up how the BRICS nations have evolved over the years with an attempt to eradicate poverty. The HDI, GDP, CPI and labour productivity were indicators that helped to judge the same and compare as to why some countries developed faster and why others could not. As a result, the answer to the research question- The development of poverty reduction in India in the 21st century in comparison to the BRICS countries. What are the driving factors and policy implications?- is that the infrastructural development along with the growth in e-commerce, trade and market-oriented reforms were the driving factors that gave rise to the economic growth to other BRICS nations as compared to India. The trend analysis shows the relation between HDI and the other 3 factors - CPI, GDP, labour productivity. One of the main findings was that India lacked the guidance and effective policy implications which helped, for instance China, to succeed in achieving poverty reduction. A potential solution to help improve India's poverty level is that there can be an effort made to implement more efficient policies with proper supervision in order to prevent corruption from taking place. The rules and regulations can be made stricter so that people are obliged to follow them. Furthermore, there can be more employment opportunities made available along with yearly campaigns with the aim of skill development to the working population of the economy. In this manner, it might become easier to achieve lower poverty levels and improve India's living conditions.

4. LIMITATIONS

This essay looks at correlation and not cause and effect relationships, which can be considered as a limitation in the current research.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT: Dr. Timo Hummel (PhD in Economics) (Mentor)

REFERENCES

Ahluwalia, M. S. (2002). Economic reforms in India since 1991: Has gradualism worked?. *Journal of Economic perspectives*, 16(3), 67-88.

- Anikin, V., & Tikhonova, N. (2016). Poverty and inequality in BRICS Countries: The Case of Russia. *Sociological Research*, 55(5), 305-341.
- Chotia, V., & Rao, N. V. M. (2017). Investigating the interlinkages between infrastructure development, poverty and rural–urban income inequality: Evidence from BRICS nations. *Studies in Economics and Finance*, 34(4), 466-484.
- Cornia, G. (Ed.). (2006). *Pro-poor Macroeconomics: potential and limitations*. Springer.
- Edochie, I. N., Freije-Rodriguez, S., Lakner, C., Moreno Herrera, L., Newhouse, D. L., Sinha Roy, S., & Yonzan, N. (2022). What do we Know about Poverty in India in 2017/18?.
- Fan, S., Chan-Kang, C., & Mukherjee, A. (2005). *Rural and urban dynamics and poverty: Evidence from China and India* (No. 583-2016-39611).
- Fosu, A. K. (2015). Growth, inequality and poverty in Sub-Saharan Africa: recent progress in a global context. *Oxford Development Studies*, 43(1), 44-59.
- Ghosh, J. (2010). Poverty reduction in China and India: Policy implications of recent trends. *Poor Poverty*, 111.
- Karine, H. A. J. I. (2021). E-commerce development in rural and remote areas of BRICS countries. *Journal of Integrative Agriculture*, 20(4), 979-997.
- Maiorano, D., & Manor, J. (2017). Poverty reduction, inequalities and human development in the BRICS: policies and outcomes. *Commonwealth & Comparative Politics*, 55(3), 278-302.
- Massarova, A., & Potapenko, M. (2018). Approaches to poverty measurement in BRICS: a reflection on economic reality (the case of Brazil, China and Russia). *Bulletin of Geography. Socio-economic Series*, (42), 183-194.
- Naudé, W., Szirmai, A., & Haraguchi, N. (Eds.). (2015). *Structural change and industrial development in the BRICS*. OUP Oxford.

- Our World in Data. (2023). Productivity: output per hour worked. [Online]. [Accessed on 1st October 2023]. Available from: <https://ourworldindata.org/grapher/labor-productivity-per-hour-pennworldtable>
- Ravallion, M. (2011). A comparative perspective on poverty reduction in Brazil, China, and India. *The World Bank Research Observer*, 26(1), 71-104.
- Sukhadolets, T., Stupnikova, E., Fomenko, N., Kapustina, N., & Kuznetsov, Y. (2021). Foreign direct investment (FDI), investment in construction and poverty in economic crises (Denmark, Italy, Germany, Romania, China, India and Russia). *Economies*, 9(4), 152.
- World Bank Open Data. (2023). World Bank Open Data. [Online]. [Accessed on 28th September 2023]. Available from: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.MKTP.CD?locations=CN-RU-IN-ZA-BR>
- World Bank Open Data. (2023). World Bank Open Data. [Online]. [Accessed on 28th September 2023]. Available from: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/FP.CPI.TOTL.ZG?locations=CN-RU-IN-ZA-BR>
- The World Bank. (2023). World Development Indicators. [Online]. [Accessed on 28th September 2023]. Available from: <https://databank.worldbank.org/source/world-development-indicators/Series/NY.GDP.DEFL.ZS>
- Zhang, T., Zhang, Y., Wan, G., & Wu, H. (2020). Poverty reduction in China and India: a comparative study. *The Singapore Economic Review*, 65(supp01), 95-115.
- Zuo, C. (2022). Integrating devolution with centralization: A comparison of poverty alleviation programs in India, Mexico, and China. *Journal of Chinese Political Science*, 27(2), 247-270.

APPENDIX

Table 6: shows the correlation matrix of HDI, CPI, LabProd, Real GDP in Brazil

	HDI.	CPI	LabPro d	Real GDP
HDI	1			
CPI	-0.1765	1		
LabProd	-0.4893	0.0775	1	
Real GDP	-0.7261	0.2768	0.2867	1

Table 7: shows the correlation matrix of HDI, CPI, LabProd, Real GDP in Russia

	HDI.	CPI	LabPro d	Real GDP
HDI	1			
CPI	-0.3137	1		
LabProd	0.2952	-0.4714	1	
Real GDP	-0.0298	-0.0388	-0.3572	1

Table 8: shows the correlation matrix of HDI, CPI, LabProd, Real GDP in India

	HDI.	CPI	LabPro d	Real GDP
HDI	1			
CPI	-0.9599	1		
LabProd	0.9483	-0.9166	1	
Real GDP	0.9303	-0.8924	0.9465	1

Table 9: shows the correlation matrix of HDI, CPI, LabProd, Real GDP in China

	HDI.	CPI	LabPro d	Real GDP

HDI	1			
CPI	-0.5493	1		
LabProd	0.9950	-0.5713	1	
Real GDP	0.9689	-0.4310	0.9454	1

Table 10: shows the correlation matrix of HDI, CPI, LabProd, Real GDP in South Africa

	HDI.	CPI	LabPro d	Real GDP
HDI	1			
CPI	0.0245	1		
LabProd	-0.7597	0.1942	1	
Real GDP	0.2093	-0.5238	-0.4229	1